

Palladium (II) Complexes with Benzimidazole and 2-Methylbenzimidazole

S. P. Ghosh and L. K. Mishra

Complex compounds of palladium (II) with benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole are reported. Palladium (II) forms complexes of three types : (1) PdL_4X_2 , when L = benzimidazole, X = Cl', I' and NO₃', but when L = 2-methylbenzimidazole, X = only Cl' or I'; (2) PdL_2X_2 , when L = benzimidazole or 2-methylbenzimidazole and X = Cl', Br', NO₂', ClO₄', $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$ ' and SCN'; and (3) PdLX_2 , where L = only 2-methylbenzimidazole and X = Cl', Br', NO₃' and ClO₄'. Complexes of type (1) are bi-univalent electrolytes in DMF solutions. The types (2) and (3) are non-electrolytes. All complexes are diamagnetic. I.r. spectra have been used to find out the coordination of different ligands.

After the first observation by Skraup¹ on the formation of copper and cobalt compounds with benzimidazole, one of us started studies on its metal complexes². Since then several workers³⁻¹² have studied metal complexes of benzimidazole and substituted benzimidazoles. From the stability constant measurements of the complexes with benzimidazole, 2-methylbenzimidazole and 2-ethylbenzimidazole, Lane and Quinlan¹³ concluded that coordination to the metal atom takes place through the unsaturated nitrogen of the imidazole ring. This has also been supported by i.r. studies¹⁴⁻¹⁶ of some metal complexes of benzimidazole and 2-substituted benzimidazoles.

In continuation of the work on benzimidazoles complexes in this laboratory, we are reporting the complexes of palladium (II) with benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole were prepared by methods described in the literature^{2,2a}.

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Benzimidazole Complexes

Bis(benzimidazolato)palladium (II) : An ammoniacal solution of palladium (II) chloride was digested with the required amount of the ligand in aqueous solution on steam bath. The cream coloured fine precipitate, obtained at pH 8-10, was filtered, washed thoroughly with hot water, and alcohol and then dried in air. The complex is insoluble in water and common organic solvents.

Tetrakis(benzimidazole)palladium (II) iodide : When a solution of palladium (II) iodide in saturated aqueous KI was treated with hot aqueous solution of the ligand, an orange yellow precipitate was obtained. This was filtered and washed with dilute KI solution and finally with hot water.

The same compound was also obtained by refluxing, for 4-5 hrs, PdI₂ in methanol with excess of ligand.

The chloride of the above tetrakis-complex was prepared by refluxing an alcoholic solution of palladium (II) chloride with excess of ligand. The resulting solution on cooling deposited a white precipitate, which was filtered and washed with alcohol and finally dried in air.

The complex nitrate was obtained as cream coloured fine crystalline precipitate when acidic palladium (II) nitrate solution was digested with aqueous solution of the ligand.

Dichlorobis (benzimidazole) palladium (II) : The cream yellow dichloro complex was obtained at pH 2-3 when an aqueous solution of palladium (II) chloride was treated with hot aqueous solution of the ligand.

Dibromobis (benzimidazole) palladium (II) : Like the dichloro complex, the dibromo complex was obtained as yellow precipitate by using palladium (II) bromide.

Dithiocyanatobis (benzimidazole) palladium (II) : The deep red solution obtained by treating an aqueous solution of palladium (II) chloride with an excess of KCNS, on digestion with hot aqueous solution of benzimidazole, gave a bright yellow precipitate (pH 2-8). This was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried in air.

Dinitrobis (benzimidazole) palladium (II) : When an ammoniacal solution of palladium (II) chloride was mixed with excess of sodium nitrite and digested on steam bath, with an aqueous solution of the ligand, a cream coloured precipitate separated (pH 7-8). This was filtered hot and washed thoroughly with water and alcohol and then dried in air.

Oxalatobis (benzimidazole) palladium (II) : The compound was obtained as cream coloured precipitate when an aqueous solution of palladium (II) chloride containing excess of oxalic acid, was refluxed on steam bath with the required amount of the ligand.

Bis(benzimidazole) palladium (II) sulphate : The complex was obtained as a white precipitate (pH 5-6) when an aqueous solution of palladium (II) sulphate was treated with an aqueous solution of the ligand and refluxed.

Bis(benzimidazole)palladium (II) perchlorate : This was obtained in the same manner as the complex sulphate using palladium (II) perchlorate.

Bis(benzimidazole)palladium (II) chloride/bromide: These were obtained like the complex sulphate using the corresponding palladium (II) halide (pH 5-6).

Benzimidazolium tetrabromopalladate (II): This compound was obtained at $pH \sim 1$, in rose red crystals when a palladium (II) bromide solution in HBr was treated with the required amount of benzimidazole. The complex is soluble in water, DMF and alcohol.

2-Methylbenzimidazole Complexes

Dinitrato(2-methylbenzimidazole)palladium (II): When an aqueous solution of palladium (II) nitrate was refluxed on the stem bath with an aqueous solution of the ligand for about an hour, a cream yellow precipitate separated (pH 2-4). The product was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and was then dissolved in methanol. A yellow residue was left, when the methanol was evaporated. The complex is insoluble in water, but soluble in most of the organic solvents.

Dichloro-, dibromo-, and diperchlorato(2-methylbenzimidazole)palladium (II): These complexes were prepared using the same procedure as used for the preparation of dinitrato(2-methylbenzimidazole)palladium (II) as described above.

Bis(2-methylbenzimidazolato)palladium (II) dihydrate; Tetrakis(2-methylbenzimidazole)palladium (II) chloride and iodide; Dichloro-, dibromo-, dinitro and dithiocyanato-bis(2-methylbenzimidazole)palladium (II); Bis(2-methylbenzimidazole)palladium(II)sulphate and perchlorate; and 2-Methylbenzimidazolium tetrachloro/tetrabromopalladate (II): All the above compounds were prepared in the same way as the corresponding benzimidazole complexes. In case of diacido-complexes, precipitation takes place at higher pH (4-6) and the precipitates are filtered without digestion. 2-Methylbenzimidazolium tetrachloropalladate (II) was prepared like the corresponding tetrabromo-complex at $pH \sim 1$ from HCl solution.

RESULTS OF ANALYSES AND PHYSICAL MEASUREMENTS

The results of chemical analyses are shown in Tables Ia and Ib. Molar conductivities of the complexes in DMF were determined between temperatures 28° and 31° and the results are shown in Table II. The i.r. spectra of some of these complexes have been recorded in KBr disc. The results are shown in Table III.

DISCUSSION

Benzimidazole is a typical monodentate ligand in acid or alcoholic medium, and has been found to form complexes with palladium (II) where two or four ligand molecules take part. 2-Methylbenzimidazole, however, forms three types of complexes with palladium (II) containing one, two and four molecules of the ligand. Both benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole show analogous behaviour in alcoholic medium and form tetrakis-complexes. There is, however, marked difference in the coordinating behaviour of these two ligands in acid solutions. In acid medium (pH 2-4), at reflux temperature, 2-methylbenzimidazole acts as a bidentate ligand and forms stable complexes of the general formula $[Pd(C_5H_6N_2)X_2]$, where $X = Cl', Br', ClO_4'$ and NO_3' . In contrast, benzimidazole did not form such complexes. Because of the presence of the methyl group in 2-position, 2-methylbenzimidazole has $pK = 6.29$, while that of benzimidazole is 5.88.¹³ Thus the behaviour of 2-methylbenzimidazole is expected to be different from that of benzimidazole to some degree.

TABLE Ia

Benzimidazole Complexes

Complexes	% Pd		% N		% anion		% H ₂ O	
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1. [Pd(C ₇ H ₅ N ₂) ₂].H ₂ O	29.88	29.66	15.56	15.62	—	—	5.21	5.02
2. [PdL ₄]I ₂	12.80	12.78	13.46	13.45	30.53	30.48	—	—
3. [PdL ₄]Cl ₂ .2EtOH	14.83	14.38	14.99	15.14	9.96	9.58	12.09 (Loss of C ₂ H ₅ OH)	12.41
4. [PdL ₄](NO ₃) ₂	15.38	15.14	19.98	19.92	—	—	—	—
5. [PdL ₂ Cl ₂]	25.89	25.73	13.52	13.55	17.44	17.14	—	—
6. [PdL ₂ Br ₂]	21.32	21.18	11.19	11.15	32.01	31.80	—	—
7. [PdL ₂ (SCN) ₂]	23.33	23.19	18.39	18.32	—	—	—	—
8. [PdL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	24.52	24.48	19.39	19.33	—	—	—	—
9. [PdL ₂ C ₂ O ₄].H ₂ O	23.89	23.71	12.40	12.48	19.42	19.62	3.76	4.03
10. [PdL ₂]SO ₄ .H ₂ O	23.37	23.29	12.18	12.27	21.34	21.03	4.21	3.94
11. [PdL ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	19.82	19.65	10.33	10.35	—	—	—	—
12. [PdL ₂]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	23.68	23.66	12.58	12.46	15.62	15.77	8.29	8.01
13. [PdL ₂]Br ₂ .2H ₂ O	20.08	19.76	10.48	10.40	30.08	29.68	—	—
14. (C ₇ H ₆ N ₂ H ⁺) ₂ [PdBr ₄]	16.00	16.02	8.49	8.43	48.54	48.11	—	—

L = Benzimidazole = C₇H₆N₂

TABLE Ib

2-Methylbenzimidazole Complexes

Complexes	% Pd		% N		% anion		% H ₂ O	
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1. [Pd(C ₈ H ₇ N ₂) ₂].2H ₂ O	26.32	26.29	13.78	13.84	—	—	8.65	8.90
2. [PdL ₄]Cl ₂	15.18	15.07	15.98	15.87	10.24	10.04	—	—
3. [PdL ₄]I ₂	12.12	11.97	12.62	12.61	28.48	28.55	—	—
4. [PdL ₂ Cl ₂].2H ₂ O	22.28	22.27	11.79	11.73	14.50	14.84	—	—
5. [PdL ₂ Br ₂].H ₂ O	19.36	19.40	10.11	10.21	29.33	29.76	3.54	3.28
6. [PdL ₂ (SCN) ₂]	21.99	21.85	17.26	17.26	—	—	—	—
7. [PdL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	23.12	23.00	18.21	18.16	—	—	—	—
8. [PdL(NO ₃) ₂]	29.51	29.35	15.25	15.45	—	—	—	—
9. [PdLCl ₂]	34.42	34.38	9.05	9.05	22.71	22.91	—	—
10. [PdLBr ₂]	26.89	26.71	7.07	7.03	39.72	40.12	—	—
11. [PdL(ClO ₄) ₂].H ₂ O	23.46	23.36	6.02	6.15	—	—	4.19	3.95
12. [PdL ₂]SO ₄ .2H ₂ O	21.30	21.06	11.01	11.12	18.78	19.10	7.22	7.16
13. [PdL ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O	17.53	17.56	9.26	9.25	32.26	32.84	—	—
14. (LH) ₂ [PdCl ₄]	20.88	20.68	10.88	10.89	27.78	27.56	—	—
15. (LH) ₂ [PdBr ₄]	15.52	15.34	8.10	8.09	46.50	46.17	—	—

L = 2-Methylbenzimidazole = C₈H₈N₂.

TABLE II
Molar Conductance in DMF (10⁻³ M soln.)
 Temp. = 28-31°

Complex	in ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻² mole ⁻¹ L = benzimidazole	in ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻² mole ⁻¹ L = 2-methylbenzimidazole
1. [PdL ₄](NO ₃) ₂	171	—
2. [PdL ₄]Cl ₂	165*	152
3. [PdL ₄]I ₂	156	148
4. [PdL ₂ Cl ₂]	20	15
5. [PdL ₂ Br ₂]	12	10
6. [PdL ₂ (SCN) ₂]	7	7
7. [PdL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	8	7
8. [PdL ₂ C ₂ O ₄].H ₂ O	11	—
9. [PdLCl ₂]	—	8
10. [PdLBr ₂]	—	15
11. [PdL(NO ₃) ₂]	—	17
12. [PdL(ClO ₄) ₂]	—	19
13. (LH) ₂ [PdCl ₄]	—	144
14. (LH) ₂ [PdBr ₄]	152	140

* Here the value indicates the conductance of [PdL₄]Cl₂.2EtOH.

It has been found that the formation of ionic, non-ionic or inner-metallic complexes is *pH* dependent. At lower *pH* (~1), both benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole behave as cations and form complexes as (C₇H₆N₂H⁺)₂[PdBr₄], and (C₈H₈N₂H⁺)₂[PdX₄], where X = Cl' or Br'. In the *pH* range 2-3, benzimidazole forms non-ionic complexes of the type [Pd(C₇H₆N₂)₂X₂], where X = Cl' or Br'. The complexes of the stoichiometry, [Pd(C₈H₈N₂)X₂] where X = Cl', Br', NO₂' and ClO₄', and [Pd(C₈H₈N₂)₂X₂], where X = Cl' or Br', are formed at *pH* 2-4 and 4-6 respectively. The complexes [Pd(C₇H₆N₂)₂(NO₂)₂] and [Pd(C₈H₈N₂)₂(NO₂)₂] are isolated at *pH* 7-8 in presence of excess of sodium nitrite but the complexes are stable up to *pH* 2. The complexes [Pd(C₇H₆N₂)₂(SCN)₂] and [Pd(C₈H₈N₂)₂(SCN)₂] are formed within *pH* 2-8.

In alkaline solution (*pH* 8-10), the N-H is deprotonated and inner-metallic chelates are obtained. [Pd(C₇H₅N₂)₂].H₂O and [Pd(C₈H₇N₂)₂].2H₂O have been isolated as fine cream coloured crystals from ammoniacal palladium (II) chloride solution. Both the compounds become anhydrous at 110°; it can, therefore, be presumed that water molecules are not coordinated. The deprotonation of N-H is further supported by the disappearance of the infra-red N-H stretching frequency (3060 cm⁻¹, 3130 cm⁻¹) in these chelates. The non-ionic character of [Pd(C₈H₇N₂)₂].2H₂O in DMF is supported by the very negligible

TABLE III

i.r. results

Benzimidazole Complexes	2-Methylbenzimidazole Complexes	Absorption bands
[PdL ₂ (SCN) ₂]	[PdL ₂ (SCN) ₂]	
3060 sp.b.	3138 m.b.	N-H Stretch, C-H Stretch.
2118 v.s.	2118 v.s.	C = N Stretch.
1613 m	1597 m	C = N Stretch.
710 sp.	720 m.s.	C-S Stretch.
[PdL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	[PdL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	
3060 sp.b.	3150 b.	N-H Stretch, C-H Stretch.
1613 m	1597 m	C = N Stretch.
1536 v.s.	1546 v.s.	NO ₂ Asymmetric Stretch.
1283 v.s.	1281 v.s.	NO ₂ Symmetric Stretch.
835 sp.	825 m	NO ₂ deformation.
[PdL ₄](NO ₃) ₂	[PdL(NO ₃) ₂]	
3080	3120	N-H Stretch.
1607 m	1591 m	C = N Stretch.
1380 v.s.	1530 v.s.	NO ₂ Asymmetric Stretch.
...	1270 v.s.	NO ₂ Symmetric Stretch.
828 m	818 m	NO ₂ deformation
[PdL ₂ C ₂ O ₄]H ₂ O	[PdL(ClO ₄) ₂]	
3610 b.		
3130 m	3095	N-H Stretch, C-H Stretch.
1670 m.b. (C=O stretch)		
1610 s.b.	1595 m	C = N Stretch.
	1135 s.b.	ClO Asymmetric band.
	1050 s.b.	ClO ₃ Symmetric band.
	935 m	ClO Stretch.
	627 s.	
	610 m.	
[PdL ₄]Cl ₂ 2EtOH		
3510 s OH Stretch		
3120 m.b. N-H Stretch.		

s, strong; sp, sharp; v, very; m, medium; b, broad.
All frequencies are in cm.⁻¹.

conductance. The molar conductance value, 7 ohm⁻¹ cm⁻² mol⁻¹ at 30°, falls well within the range of conductance exhibited by non-electrolytes in DMF as reported by Quagliano *et al.*¹⁷ and later by Basolo *et al.*¹⁸.

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The complexes of the type $[\text{PdL}_4]\text{X}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{benzimidazole}$ or $2\text{-methylbenzimidazole}$; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}'$ or I') are formed when alcoholic solution of the ligand is refluxed with corresponding palladium (II) halide in alcohol. Tetrakis-iodide can also be obtained from an aqueous solution of PdI_2 in excess of KI . No such tetrakis-halide could be isolated in aqueous medium. Tetrakis(benzimidazole)-palladium (II) nitrate was isolated from acidic palladium (II) nitrate solution. 2-Methylbenzimidazole did not form tetrakis-complex nitrate, but instead forms a nitrate complex containing only one molecule of the ligand. The electrical conductance value of the tetrakis-complexes, as shown in Table H, fall within the range reported for bivalent electrolytes^{17,18}. The i.r. spectra of the tetrakis-complexes show the N-H frequency in almost the same position or only slightly lower than it is in the free ligand. The coordination through the tertiary nitrogen is denoted by fall in $\text{C} = \text{N}$ stretching frequency of the free ligand (1668 cm^{-1}) to about 1610 cm^{-1} in these complexes. In case of $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_4]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{EtOH}$, there is a new band at 3510 cm^{-1} , which is ascribed to the alcohol adduct.¹⁹ In the i.r. spectra of $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$, only absorption frequency of uncoordinated NO'_3 could be observed. The band of medium intensity at 828 cm^{-1} and a very strong band at 1380 cm^{-1} are the typical of ν_3 and ν_2 frequencies of the uncoordinated nitrate group.²⁴ In the case of $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, the absorption frequencies at 818 cm^{-1} , 1270 cm^{-1} and 1530 cm^{-1} definitely establish the coordination of NO'_3 .²⁰⁻²⁴

The complexes of the type $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2\text{X}_2]$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}'$, Br' and $\frac{1}{2}\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, are isolated as cream yellow precipitate in the pH range 2-3. The complexes are soluble in DMF but do not show any conductivity. In the i.r. spectrum of $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$, appearance of a new band at 1670 cm^{-1} ($\text{C} = \text{O}$ stretch) confirms the oxalate group to be coordinated.²⁵ It was not possible to get any information regarding the coordination of halogens, as i.r. spectra were recorded between 4000 cm^{-1} and 400 cm^{-1} only.

The complexes $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2]\text{X}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}'$ or Br') are obtained at pH 5-6. The buff coloured compounds, $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2]\text{X}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}'$ or Br'), are converted to a cream yellow variety $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2\text{X}_2]$ at lower pH (2-3). The compounds are insoluble in water and organic solvents. The water molecules of the hydrated complexes are lost below 120° without any decomposition. Thus it appears that in these complexes, benzimidazole functions as a bidentate ligand. Attempts to prepare complexes of stoichiometry $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2\text{X}_2$ or $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)_2\text{X}_2$, where $\text{X} = \text{I}'$ or NO'_3 , were unsuccessful and instead $[\text{PdL}_4]\text{I}_2$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$ were obtained.

The behaviour of 2-methylbenzimidazole in aqueous solution is not similar to benzimidazole. Dichloro- and dibromo-bis(2-methylbenzimidazole)palladium (II), $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)_2\text{X}_2]$ are formed immediately at pH 4-6 at ordinary temperature. When, however, the

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preparation is carried out at steam temperature, a bulky precipitate of dichloro- or dibromo-(2-methylbenzimidazole)palladium (II), $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)\text{X}_2]$ are produced when the $p\text{H}$ comes to 2-4. The conductance data of PdL_2X_2 and PdLX_2 , where $\text{L} = 2\text{-methylbenzimidazole}$ and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}'$ or Br' , support their formulation as $[\text{PdL}_2\text{X}_2]$ and $[\text{PdLX}_2]$. Thus it appears that the ligand behaves as bidentate molecule in the latter complex. The bidentate behaviour of the ligand has also been reported by M. V. Arlenenko *et al.*²⁶

Diperechlorato(2-methylbenzimidazole)palladium (II), $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)(\text{ClO}_4)_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$, gives a non-conducting solution in DMF. In the i.r. spectrum, the absorption frequencies of perchlorate at 1120 cm^{-1} and 625 cm^{-1} split up into two components each at 1135 cm^{-1} , 1050 cm^{-1} and 627 cm^{-1} , 610 cm^{-1} , which is ascribed to perchlorate coordination as has been reported by Hathaway and Underhill.²⁷

Benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole both form orange yellow dithiocyanato-complexes, $[\text{PdL}_2(\text{SCN})_2]$, under identical conditions which are non-conducting in DMF solution. In the i.r. spectra, a very intense absorption is observed at 2118 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretch) for both the complexes. A sharp medium band is observed at 710 cm^{-1} (C-S stretch) for $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2(\text{SCN})_2]$ and a weak band at 720 cm^{-1} for $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)_2(\text{SCN})_2]$, lead to the conclusion that SCN' is coordinated to palladium through the sulphur atom²⁸⁻³⁰, which is as expected from the soft acid character of palladium.

In the case of 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole or 2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazolinopalladium (II) thiocyanate complex, $[\text{PdL}(\text{NCS})_2]$, the i.r. results show the coordination of thiocyanate group through nitrogen (820 cm^{-1} or 828 cm^{-1} , C-S stretch).³¹ Here the soft character of palladium has been altered through coordination with 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole or 2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazoline.

The cream coloured dinitro-complexes, $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$, were isolated from the neutral solution under identical conditions and are non-electrolytes. In the i.r. spectra, the values of $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NO}_2)$, $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NO}_2)$ and $\delta(\text{NO}_2)$ (Table III) definitely prove the monocoordination of nitro group, which are in accord with the reported literatures.³²⁻³⁵

M.V. Arlenenko *et al.*²⁶ have reported the cation-like behaviour of 2-methylbenzimidazole. Goodgame and co-workers have also studied such cationic complexes of benzimidazole. Palladium (II) in high acid concentration ($p\text{H} \sim 1$) form compounds of general

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formula $(LH)_2[PdX_4]$ (where $L = C_7H_6N_2$, $X = Br'$ only; when $L = C_8H_8N_2$, $X_1 = Cl'$ or Br'). These compounds are isolated in brown or red crystalline plates and are soluble in water, alcohol and DMF. Aqueous solutions of these compounds are unstable and undergo hydrolysis :

The observation is confirmed by high molar conductance, 450 ohm^{-1} in aqueous solution (152 ohm^{-1} in DMF). The i.r. spectra (4000 cm^{-1} — 400 cm^{-1}) of these complexes are almost identical with those of the ligands, which supports the uncoordinated nature of the ligand molecules.

Thanks are due to Professor J. N. Chatterjea and Dr. U. C. Agarwal for recording some i.r. spectra, and to Principal N. S. Nagendranath, for constant encouragement. Acknowledgement is also made to the U. G. C., New Delhi, for some financial aid.

Chemical Laboratory,
Science College,
Patna University,
Patna-5.

Received January 10, 1969